

Microwave-mediated Green synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives against inflammatory disease

Biswa Mohan Sahoo^{a*}, Jnyanaranjan Panda^b, Bimal Krishna Banik^c and Binayani Sahoo^a

^aDepartment of Pharmacy, Vikas Group of Institution, Nunna-521 212, Vijayawada Rural, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail: drbiswamohansahoo@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Roland Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Berhampur-760 010, Odisha, India

^cCommunity Health System of South Texas, Edinburg, Texas 78539, USA

Manuscript received 30 September 2018, accepted 01 November 2018

A rapid and efficient microwave-mediated Green synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives (**2a-e**) is described based on reaction between benzohydrazide and various substituted benzoic acids. The use of microwave irradiation to carry out chemical reactions provides pollution free and eco-friendly system with formation of pure products. The structural elucidation of newly synthesized compounds is based on their spectral data such as IR and ¹H NMR. The titled compounds are screened for their anti-inflammatory activity. Some of the compounds displayed significant anti-inflammatory activity than the standard drug.

Keywords: Microwave, Green synthesis, oxadiazole, inflammation, spectral data.

1. Introduction

The oxadiazole nucleus is an important class of heterocyclic compounds present in various synthetic and natural products with diverse pharmacological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, anti-tumor, anti-malarial, anti-mycobacterial, anti-asthmatic, antidepressant, anticonvulsant, antiviral, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, analgesic and anti-inflammatory, etc.¹⁻⁴. Oxadiazoles possess one oxygen and two nitrogen atoms in a five membered ring with molecular formula C₂H₂N₂O⁵⁻⁷. There are four isomers of oxadiazole such as 1,2,3-oxadiazole, 1,2,4-oxadiazole, 1,2,5-oxadiazole, 1,3,4-oxadiazole⁸⁻¹⁰. Out of these, 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives are well known due to presence of this pharmacophore in various medicinal agents such as Raltegravir, Nesapidil, Fenadiazole, Furamizole, Zibotentan etc.¹¹⁻¹⁴. 1,3,4-Oxadiazole contains one oxygen and two nitrogen atoms at 1st, 3rd and 4th position of the heterocyclic ring system¹⁵.

Several research groups have developed different methods for the synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives by using conventional heating method. For conventional heating, oil, water or sand bath are used as energy source. However, these processes are time consuming and product yield is very less

due to formation of impurities or byproduct. Therefore, a clean, convenient and eco-friendly method is followed for the synthesis of oxadiazoles derivatives^{16,17}. This method increases rate of reaction, minimizes reaction time with formation of pure products. The generation of heterocyclic rings by cyclo-condensation reactions can be carried out smoothly by microwave heating¹⁸. Therefore, oxadiazole derivatives (**2a-e**) are produced by cyclo-condensation of benzohydrazide with various substituted benzoic acids under microwave irradiation for 7-12 min. Benzohydrazide is produced by esterification of benzoic acid with ethanol in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid followed by reaction with hydrazine hydrate. The structure of newly synthesized compounds is confirmed by their spectral data such as IR and ¹H NMR. These compounds were evaluated for their anti-inflammatory activity and compared with the standard drug.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials:

All the required chemicals were purchased from E. Merck. All the melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The completion of the synthesis was checked by TLC on pre-coated silica gel-aluminum plates (Type 60

Fig 1. Structure of clinically useful drugs containing 1,3,4-oxadiazole scaffold.

Fig. 2. Nomenclature of 1,3,4-oxadiazole nucleus with its structure showing plane, centroid and exclusion sphere.

F254, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and were visualized by exposure to UV-light (254 nm) or iodine vapor for few seconds. The synthesized products were recrystallized from ethanol as a solvent. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer, model IR Affinity-1 (Schimadzu), using KBr powder and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra of the selected compounds were recorded on FT-NMR spectrometer, model Advance-II (Bruker), (at 400 MHz) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. The multiplicities of the signals are de-

noted with the symbols *s*, *d*, *t* and *m* for singlet, doublet, triplet and multiplet respectively. The synthesis was carried out by conventional and microwave heating. By using microwave irradiation, the synthesis was carried out at power level-2, which corresponds to power level 210 W.

2.2. Methods:

2.2.1. Conventional synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives (2a-e):

Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantity of benzohydrazide and various substituted benzoic acids were dissolved in ethanol (10 mL) and refluxed for 2–3 h to get the solid product of oxadiazole derivatives (4a-e). In between TLC was checked to confirm the completion of reaction. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.2.2. Microwave assisted synthesis of oxadiazole derivatives (2a-e):

The required quantities of above reactants are subjected to microwave irradiation at power level-2 (210 W) for 7–12

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of the titled compounds (2a-e).

min. In between TLC was performed to confirm the completion of reaction. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol (Scheme 1).

2.2.3. Anti-inflammatory activity:

Carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method:

Anti-inflammatory activity was performed based on carrageenan induced hind paw oedema test by Winter *et al.*^{19,20}. Acute inflammation was produced by injecting 0.1 ml of 1% carrageenan solution into sub plantar surface of rat's hind paw. Rats are randomly divided into 7 groups of 6 rats per group, fasted for 12 h with clean drinking water provided *ad libitum*. The group specific drugs were administered 1 h before the carrageenan injection. The paw volume up to the tibio-tarsal articulation was measured using Plethysmometer at basal, 1 h, 3 h and 6 h after carrageenan injection. The anti-inflammatory activity was expressed as percentage decrease in paw oedema and determined by using the following formula^{19,20}.

$$\% \text{ decrease in paw oedema} = \frac{(V_{\text{control}} - V_{\text{test}})}{V_{\text{control}}} \times 100$$

where *V* is expressed as rat paw volume.

3. Results and discussion

All the reactions were completed in 2–3 h by the conventional method, while under MWI, the same reactions were completed in 7–12 min. It was observed that the microwave mediated Green synthesis provides good product yield as compared to the conventional method. All the synthesized compounds were characterized by their physical, chemical and spectral data (Table 1). The solvents chloroform and ethyl acetate (70:30) were used as mobile phase for monitoring TLC. A comparative study in terms of yield and reaction period was presented in Table 2. In the ¹H NMR spectrum, the aromatic protons were observed as multiplet at δ 2.54–4.87, the proton of the -OH at resonated as a sharp singlet is δ 8.94.

Table 1. Characterization data of oxadiazole derivatives

Compd. Code	X	m.p. (°C)	R _f value	IR (cm ⁻¹) (KBr)
2a	4-Cl	130–134	0.63	650 (C-Cl), 1475 (CH=CH), 1597 (C=N), 3103 (C-H aromatic)
2b	2-NO ₂	130–135	0.64	1477 (CH=CH), 1566 (C-NO ₂), 1597 (C=N) 3057 (C-H aromatic)
2c	3-NO ₂	145–150	0.61	1474 (CH=CH), 1562 (C-NO ₂), 1593 (C=N) 3150 (C-H aromatic)
2d	3-OH	140–144	0.66	1479 (CH=CH), 1595 (C=N), 3067 (C-H aromatic), 3234 (OH)
2e	4-OH	150–160	0.57	1472 (CH=CH), 1592 (C=N), 3063 (C-H aromatic), 3237 (OH)

Table 2. Comparative study of conventional and microwave assisted synthesis

Compd. Code	Reaction time		Energy		Yield (%)	
	Conventional (h)	Microwave (min)	Conventional (Temp. °C)	Microwave (Power, Watt)	Conventional	Microwave
2a	2	07	100	210	56	74
2b	3	09	100	210	68	82
2c	3	10	100	210	65	83
2d	2	12	100	210	66	80
2e	3	08	100	210	57	76

Table 3. Anti-inflammatory activity of oxadiazole derivatives

Treatment groups	% inhibition \pm SEM		
	1 h	3 h	6 h
2a	37.52 \pm 1.57	52.96 \pm 1.45	59.82 \pm 1.03
2b	45.57 \pm 1.87	56.93 \pm 1.56	61.45 \pm 1.12
2c	47.73 \pm 1.51	58.65 \pm 1.37	65.32 \pm 1.21
2d	58.54 \pm 1.32	63.54 \pm 1.34	74.21 \pm 1.32
2e	53.66 \pm 1.33	66.45 \pm 1.47	77.42 \pm 1.37
Control	–	–	–
Standard (Diclofenac)	64.32 \pm 3.54	73.32 \pm 3.65	83.25 \pm 1.47

4. Conclusion

Oxadiazole derivatives are considered as promising classes of bioactive heterocyclic compounds during development of the new therapeutic molecules. There are improvements in the rate of reaction and yield of products by microwave irradiation as compared to conventional conditions. The compounds with electron withdrawing groups showed significant anti-inflammatory activity. These results proved that oxadiazole based heterocyclic compounds are found to be promising lead molecules for further synthetic and biological evaluations.

References

- S. Juan, J. A. Makawana and H. Zhu, *Mini-Reviews in Med. Chem.*, 2013, **13(12)**, 1725.
- P. Zhan and X. Liu, *Mini-Reviews in Med. Chem.*, 2011, **11(13)**, 1130.
- A. V. Adhikari and V. V. Badigar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1988, **27B**, 542.
- A. K. Singh, R. Parthasarathy and M. Lahani, *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, 2012, **4**, 779.
- M. K. Mishra, A. K. Gupta, S. Negi and M. Bhatta, *Inter. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2010, **1(3)**, 172.
- M. R. Banday, R. H. Mattoo and A. Rauf, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2010, **122(2)**, 177.
- N. Bhardwaj, S. K. Saraf, P. Sharma and P. Kumar, *E-Journal of Chemistry*, 2009, **6(4)**, 1133.
- M. A. Bakht, M. S. Yar and S. G. Abdel-Hamid, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 5862.
- V. Mickevicius, R. Vaickelioniene and B. Sapijanskaite, *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*, 2009, **45(2)**, 215.
- M. S. Y. Khan and M. Akhtar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2003, **42B**, 900.
- S. R. Pattan, P. A. Rabara, V. S. Wakale and D. S. Musmade, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2009, **48B**, 1453.
- B. S. Congeners and K. M. S. Faelelbom, *Molecules*, 2011, **16**, 4339.
- L. Freitas and J. Bruno, *Molecules*, 2012, **17**, 10192.
- M. S. Karthikeyan, D. J. Prasad, M. Mahalinga, B. S. Holl and N. S. Kumari, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **43**, 25.
- A. V. Adhikari and V. V. Badigar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1988, **27B**, 542.
- J. N. Sangshetti, A. R. Chabukswar and D. B. Shinde, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2011, **21**, 444.
- S. Sanchit and S. N. Pandeya, *IJRAP*, 2011, **2(2)** 459.
- R. J. Patel, G. C. Patel, M. M. Patel and N. J. Patel, *Indian J. Pharm. Educ. Res.*, 2007, **41(2)**, 95.
- R. A. Turner, "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academy Press, New York, 1971, 372.
- S. N. Shetty and S. M. Anika, "Laboratory manual of Pharmacology and Toxicology", 1st ed., Fourth Dimension Publishers, Enugu, 1982, 78.